

QUANTUM THREAT TO CLASSICAL CRYPTOGRAPHY: A FOCUS ON RSA**Lina KANKEVIČIENĖ**

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Abstract. Cryptography is crucial for protecting private information. However, the emergence of quantum computing poses a significant threat to the security of classical cryptographic systems. Traditional algorithms such as RSA can be vulnerable to quantum attacks. Shor's quantum algorithm can break RSA encryption in polynomial time. This article examines the RSA cryptosystem, the impact of quantum computing on cryptography, the challenges of quantum computing, and its applications in various fields. The article also presents an experiment comparing traditional and Shor factorization methods for semi-prime numbers. Although the experiment does not involve factoring extremely large numbers, it demonstrates the simplicity of implementing algorithms. By conducting experiments and analysing the results, computer science students can better understand the principles of quantum computing, its capabilities, and limitations, and develop practical skills.

Keywords: *RSA, quantum computing, Shor's algorithm, cryptography, factorization.*

Introduction

Cryptography safeguards sensitive information in various domains, such as finance, communication, and national security, by making it inaccessible to unauthorized individuals. Classical cryptographic algorithms, depend on the complexity of mathematical problems, like factoring large numbers or solving discrete logarithms, to provide secure communication channels (Stanley et al. 2022; Krishna et al. 2023). Quantum computers utilize the parallelism in qubits to solve such mathematical challenges exponentially faster than classical computers (Preskill, 2018; Willsch et al. 2023; Somsuk, 2024; Shafique et al. 2024). This paper discusses how quantum computing could revolutionize cryptography and potentially threaten current encryption algorithms such as RSA and presents a detailed experiment comparing Shor's algorithm with traditional factorization methods for small semi-prime numbers. The experiment aimed to compare the factorization speeds of Shor's algorithm and traditional methods for semi-prime numbers. Using IBM Qiskit Terra 0.23.3 and the Qiskit AER simulator, we demonstrate the practical implementation of these algorithms. This experiment serves educational purposes, helping computer science students understand quantum computing capabilities and limitations while developing practical skills. The paper provides valuable insights into the performance of Shor's algorithm for factoring semiprime numbers and the potential implications for cryptography in the quantum era. It underscores the need for continued research and development in quantum-resistant cryptographic solutions to safeguard digital security.

2. Background information on Cryptography and Quantum computing**2.1. RSA Cryptosystem**

Cryptography is the science of securing communication by transforming plain information into unintelligible data that can only be understood by the intended recipients. The RSA cryptosystem, named after its inventors Rivest, Shamir, and Adleman, is one of the earliest (introduced in 1978) and most widely used public-key cryptosystems. Its 4096 and higher-order variants are used for security and military purposes since they are considered one of the most secure options. RSA-1028 and 2048-bit encryption are also commonly used options in RSA (Sharma et al. 2020).

The RSA cryptosystem provides secure communication through public-key encryption. The RSA algorithm works as follows:

1. Key initialisation:

- Select two large prime numbers, p and q , and compute their product, $n = p \times q$, typically 2048 bits, approximately 617 digits long (Tyson, 2022).

- Compute Euler's Totient function $\phi(n) = (p - 1) \times (q - 1)$.

- Choose a public exponent e and compute a private exponent d , such that $(e \times d - 1)$ is divisible by $(p - 1)(q - 1)$.

2. Encryption: a message M is encrypted using the public key (n, e) to produce a ciphertext C (coded message) as: $C = M^e \pmod{n}$.

3. Decryption: the ciphertext C is decrypted using the private key (n, d) to recover the original message M , as: $M = C^d \pmod{n}$.

RSA serves as a cornerstone of online security, enabling secure transactions, digital signatures, and secret communication. RSA plays a pivotal role in establishing secure digital signatures, ensuring the authenticity and integrity of digital documents (Somsuk, Thakong 2020)), underpinning secure e-commerce transactions, safeguarding sensitive data, and facilitating the secure exchange of encrypted information across various platforms.

RSA algorithm establishes secure connections between web browsers and web servers, ensuring that sensitive data like login credentials and credit card information is transmitted securely (SSL/TLS protocols). It also enables encrypting and decrypting emails to protect them from unauthorized access and creating digital signatures to verify the authenticity and integrity of digital documents (Liu et al. 2022).

RSA is not only used for securing text communication but also has applications in other domains, such as image encryption. Researchers have proposed methods combining RSA with chaotic maps to enhance the security of colour image encryption. This approach introduces pixel confusion and diffusion techniques, making the encrypted images more resistant to cryptanalysis. To optimize performance, RSA can be parallelized by breaking down messages into smaller chunks and encrypting each chunk with different key pairs. This can significantly reduce encryption and decryption times, especially in high-performance computing environments (Liu et al. 2022).

2.2. Quantum computing

What is Quantum Computing? Quantum computers use quantum bits, superimposed in many states through the superposition phenomenon, to process and store information in the form of bits as 0s and 1s. These enabled quantum computers to solve problems that require multiple parallel computations at once, to perform computations much faster than classical ones, and gave solutions to a class of problems believed to have infeasible solutions by classical computers (Preskill 2018; Hossain 2023; Wang, Zhang 2021; Zohuri, Rahmani 2020). Moreover, another quantum mechanical effect, called entanglement, makes the qubits correlated with one another, thus increasing their processing capacity (Liu 2023; Zohuri, Rahmani 2020). Quantum computing holds great promise to transform several industries by solving problems currently proven to be intractable for classical computers (Boutin 2022).

Shor's algorithm. Shor's algorithm, developed by the American mathematician Peter Shor in 1994, is a quantum algorithm with the potential to factorize large numbers significantly faster than classical algorithms (Proctor, Kendon 2016; Singh, Sakk 2024, Bernstein et al. 2009). It is a revolutionary algorithm due to its implications for breaking traditional cryptographic systems, such as RSA, by efficiently factorizing large numbers on a quantum computer. The algorithm's operation involves finding the prime factors of an integer N , which is a computationally intensive task for classical computers. Shor's algorithm is based on the rules of quantum mechanics like superposition and entanglement. It can theoretically factorize large numbers in polynomial time and therefore traditional cryptographic systems using RSA encryption are under severe threat.

3. The Impact of Quantum Computing on RSA Security

3.1. RSA cryptosystem issues due to quantum computing

The primary threat to RSA posed by quantum computing lies in its ability to efficiently factor large numbers using Shor's algorithm (Buchanan, Woodward 2017; Gidney, Fowler 2019; Bernstein et al. 2009; Sharma et al. 2020). Shor's algorithm uses the quantum Fourier transform to factorize large numbers efficiently. The number of qubits required to factorize an RSA key depends on its length, with a 2048-bit key requiring millions of qubits. Creating logical qubits that can resist errors requires millions of physical qubits, making large-scale, fault-tolerant quantum computing a distant goal (Hossain 2023; Sahu, Mazumdar 2024; Proctor, Kendon 2016).

Currently, various nation-states and individuals are intercepting and storing encrypted data in anticipation of future quantum computers. This pre-emptive strategy, known as "harvest now, decrypt later," expects that quantum computers within the next ten to twenty years will be capable of breaking currently existing encryption algorithms like RSA. This would undermine RSA security, which relies on the computational difficulty of factoring large numbers. Recognizing this threat, the U.S. Congress has mandated a transition to quantum-resistant cryptographic methods (NIST project).

3.2. Challenges in Quantum Computing Development

Quantum computers have evolved from theoretical ideas into real machines that can outperform classical systems in certain tasks. For example, Google's Sycamore quantum processor achieved quantum supremacy in 2019 by performing a specific quantum computation that would have taken classical supercomputers thousands of years to complete. This indicates the solution of a highly specialized and artificial problem, rather than a broad practical application to problem-solving (Gupta 2002). The development and deployment of Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) demonstrate the increasing impact of quantum technologies in real-world applications, including finance, government, and healthcare, to protect sensitive financial transactions, government communications, and healthcare data (Jain et al. 2016; Buchanan, Woodward 2017; Stanley et al. 2022; Krishna al. 2023; Singh 2021). QKD doesn't require the same type of large-scale quantum computers needed to break RSA encryption. It operates on a different principle, focusing on secure key exchange by ensuring that any attempt to eavesdrop on the communication alters the quantum states being transmitted, thus making the attack detectable (Jain et al. 2016).

Quantum computers still face challenges:

Error rates and noise. Current quantum systems, known as Noisy Intermediate-Scale Quantum (NISQ) systems, are not yet capable of full fault-tolerant quantum computation (Proctor, Kendon 2016; Buchanan, Woodward 2017; Corcoles et al. 2019, Moussa et al. 2020). NISQ devices rely on qubits, which are susceptible to errors due to noise and decoherence (Sarma 2022). These errors arise from the qubits' interaction with their environment, causing them to lose their quantum superposition and become classical states (decoherence) or introducing noise during computations (error). This limits their ability to perform accurate calculations. NISQ devices do not have the necessary Quantum error correction (QEC) mechanisms to achieve full fault tolerance. This means that errors can accumulate and eventually render the computation unreliable.

Scalability. Current systems typically have around 50 to a few hundred qubits, which are not sufficient to run complex algorithms like Shor's algorithm on the scale needed to break RSA encryption.

Quantum hardware. Different hardware platforms, such as superconducting qubits, trapped ions, and quantum dots, each have their own unique materials challenges that can affect the scalability, performance, and stability of the qubits (de Leon et al. 2021). Major companies, including IBM, Google, and Intel, are working on developing quantum processors with more qubits and lower error rates (Leon et al. 2021).

Algorithmic Challenges. Designing efficient quantum algorithms is a complex task that demands a profound understanding of both quantum mechanics and the specific problem domain.

Quantum circuit complexity, noise and decoherence, and hybrid quantum-classical algorithms are key factors to consider when developing effective quantum algorithms.

3.3. Attempts to mitigate the dangers of Quantum computing on Cryptography

The development of quantum computing is progressing rapidly and experts predict that quantum computers capable of breaking RSA encryption could be built in the near future (Chen et al. 2016). To solve these threats, a process is underway to develop post-quantum cryptographic standards that could be resilient against quantum attacks. The National Institute

of Standards and Technology (NIST) is leading a global effort to develop post-quantum cryptography (PQC) algorithms. The two most important steps to safer security against Quantum computers include the development of post-quantum cryptographic algorithms and their standardization, which would ensure the resilience of cryptographic systems and maintain the security of digital communications in the era of quantum computing.

To address the vulnerabilities posed by quantum computing, researchers are developing post-quantum cryptographic algorithms designed to be resistant to quantum attacks and ensure the continued security of digital communication and data in the face of the quantum threat. These include lattice-based, hash-based, and multivariate polynomial cryptographic systems, which do not rely on integer factorization or discrete logarithms, making them immune to Shor's algorithm. Hybrid systems that combine classical and quantum-resistant components are being explored as interim solutions while full quantum-resistant cryptography is developed (Holden 2022; Buchanan, Woodward 2017).

4. Implementing of Shor's algorithm and traditional factorization methods

The experiment aimed to investigate the efficiency of Shor's algorithm, a quantum algorithm designed for factoring numbers 9, 15, 21 and 25 and compare it to traditional factorization methods. By analysing the factorization times for different semiprime numbers, the study sought to understand the potential vulnerabilities of classical cryptographic systems to quantum attacks.

By achieving these objectives, the experiment contributes to a better understanding of the challenges and opportunities posed by quantum computing for cryptography. The experiment may be conducted for educational purposes. This would help CS students understand the capabilities, limitations and applications of quantum computing.

Methodology. To perform an experiment, IBM Qiskit was utilized due to its superior documentation compared to Microsoft Azure and Amazon Braket. Furthermore, Qiskit version 0.42.0 was chosen for its inclusion of Shor's algorithm, which is necessary in this experiment. The Jupyter Lab IDE and Python were selected as recommended by Qiskit documentation for seamless integration and efficient coding.

Experimental Setup:

1) The numbers 9, 15, 21 and 25 were chosen as uneven semiprimes up to 33. Semiprimes 33 and above were excluded due to the indefinite time required for factorization using Shor's algorithm.

2) The calculations were conducted on a system with an Intel i5-12400F processor, 16GB RAM operating at 3200MHz. This setup ensured optimal performance for running simulations and algorithms.

Software Tools:

1) IBM Qiskit: Utilized for quantum computing simulations and Shor's algorithm implementation.

2) Jupyter Lab IDE: Chosen for its compatibility with Qiskit and Python, facilitating code development and analysis.

3) Python: Programming language used for implementing algorithms and data analysis.

Algorithm Implementation:

1) Shor's Algorithm: Implemented from Qiskit Terra 0.23.3, using Qiskit's AER quantum simulator as the backend to factorize the selected semiprime numbers efficiently.

2) Traditional Factorization: Utilized by using existing code snippet sourced from GeekforGeeks website to compare the performance against Shor's algorithm.

Experimental Procedure:

1) Input the selected semiprime numbers (9, 15, 21, 25) for analysis.

2) Implement Shor's algorithm using Qiskit, with the AER quantum simulator as the backend.

3) Record the average time from 20 attempts taken to factorize each semiprime number.

4) Input the selected semiprime numbers (9, 15, 21, 25) for analysis again.

5) Implement the traditional factorization method and record the average factorization duration 20 times.

The traditional factoring algorithm is adapted from the *GeeksforGeeks* website. The factoring *Shor's* algorithm was implemented while referring to IBM Quantum Documentation (SHOR | IBM Quantum Documentation).

The traditional factoring algorithm is a basic implementation of the trial division algorithm, which is a straightforward approach to factoring numbers. While it's easy to understand and implement, it's important to note that it's not the most efficient method for factoring large numbers. The General Number Field Sieve (GNFS) is the most efficient known

classical algorithm for factoring large integers, particularly those used in RSA cryptography. It's a complex algorithm that involves number theory and linear algebra, but it's significantly more efficient than simpler methods like trial division. However, for educational purposes and smaller numbers, the trial division algorithm can be a useful tool for understanding the concept of factorization and its challenges.

The chosen algorithm may not be the most efficient for factoring large numbers. The code prioritizes simplicity over optimal performance. More efficient but complex algorithms exist.

1) Experimental results and analysis

- Compare the factorization times of Shor's algorithm with traditional methods for each semiprime number.
- Summarize the findings regarding the susceptibility of cryptography to quantum computers versus traditional computers based on the experimental results.

2) Data presentation.

Table 1

Factorization times of the selected semiprimes in seconds, via Traditional and Shor's algorithms

Semiprimes	Traditional	Shor
9	7.05×10^{-7} s	6.68×10^{-6} s
15	8.00×10^{-7} s	4.51 s
21	9.05×10^{-7} s	19 s
25	7.95×10^{-7} s	4.55×10^{-6} s

Fig. 1 shows the information from Table 1, the left axis is the time of the traditional factorization algorithm and the right axis is the time of the Shor algorithm.

Fig. 1. Factorization times of the selected semiprimes in seconds, via Traditional and Shor's algorithms

The graph and table illustrate the stark contrast between the factorization times when using traditional computing methods versus Shor's algorithm, implemented via Qiskit in a simulated AER Quantum environment. The selected semiprimes for this analysis were 9, 15, 21 and 25. Notably, the traditional method shows relatively consistent factorization times for all numbers, ranging from approximately 7.05×10^{-7} seconds for the number 9 to about 9.05×10^{-7} seconds for the number 21. This consistency underlines the predictability and stability of traditional factorization methods when dealing with numbers of this scale.

In contrast, Shor's algorithm displays a wide difference in factorization times. For the numbers 9 and 25, the algorithm quickly factors them in approximately 6.68×10^{-6} and 4.55×10^{-6} seconds, respectively. These times are only marginally longer than those of the traditional method, showcasing the efficiency of Shor's algorithm for these specific semiprimes. However, the numbers 15 and 21 present a dramatically different picture, with factorization times of 4.51 and 19 seconds, respectively.

Analysis. As seen in Figure 1 and Table 1, Shor's algorithm's efficiency in factorizing semiprimes is influenced by the inherent mathematical characteristics of the numbers. Specifically, semiprimes composed of identical prime factors, such as 9 (3×3) and 25 (5×5),

are factorized more rapidly by Shor's algorithm compared to semiprimes with distinct prime factors, such as 15 (3x5) and 21 (3x7). This distinction can be attributed to the algorithm's ability to exploit the periodicity in modular exponentiation more effectively when the semiprime is a square of a prime number.

Shor's algorithm, utilizing quantum parallelism and the principles of quantum Fourier transform, excels in identifying the periodicity of the modular function $a^x \bmod N$, where N is the semiprime in question and a is a randomly chosen number less than N (Singleton 2023). Its efficiency in handling squares of primes comes from the algorithm's inherent design to exploit the structure of the problem's solution space, where the periodicity is more pronounced and easier to detect in the quantum state. This quantum phenomenon underpins the high performance of the algorithm concerning the uniform factorization times perceived in semiprimes made up of squared primes. Traditional algorithms are treated as deterministic, providing results that are more rarely subjected to performance variance or deterioration to the mathematical properties of semiprime. They are consistent but not concerning scalability, especially for an increasing size of semiprime. So, there is a basic limitation in the large-scale cryptographic problem.

This can be further seen via a comparison of Neven's and Moore's laws. Neven's Law suggests that quantum computing power is increasing at a doubly exponential rate, far outpacing Moore's Law, which has historically described the exponential growth of classical computing power. Specifically, Neven's Law indicates that the capabilities of quantum processors are growing at a rate much faster than the doubling of transistors on integrated circuits every two years, as stated by Moore's Law. This rapid development in quantum computation, supported by the invention of the Shor algorithm, thus supports a big shift in computational paradigms.

Thus, even if the analysis reveals that quantum computers cannot pose issues in cryptography at the time being in terms of security, the future landscape above the laws could dramatically change because of the laws above. Such cryptography protocols used to secure digital communications in use today may even get defeated very soon with the development of quantum computers. This looming threat, therefore, calls for the development and adoption of quantum-resistant cryptographic algorithms that can guarantee security from attacks either way—classical or quantum. This shift toward post-quantum cryptography thus represents not just the necessity for novel algorithm design but also an appeal to ensuring protocols developed with these new algorithms are fit to be added to current systems without impairing efficiency or security. That becomes much more urgent as the information being intercepted today, if encrypted, will at some future date be decrypted by sufficiently powerful quantum computers. These, therefore, by implication, mean the long-term security implications that quantum computing may have on cryptography are deep and therefore, it requires very proactive ways and means of securing digital security in the upcoming quantum era.

Conclusions

Exploring the performance of Shor's algorithm with semiprime numbers lights up a critical point for cryptographers. Studying the efficiency of semiprime factorization, especially those which are squared primes, presents a pressing need for a change toward means that are resistant to quantum. As quantum computer technology rapidly advances, traditional cryptographic paradigms based on prime factorization are increasingly vulnerable.

The development and deployment of quantum-resistant cryptographic standards have become a pressing priority. NIST's initiative to establish post-quantum cryptographic frameworks is crucial for safeguarding digital communications in the era of quantum computing. Transitioning to new cryptographic paradigms is essential to maintain the integrity of sensitive information.

Shor's algorithm demonstrates the potential of quantum computing to revolutionize cryptography. It can efficiently break RSA and other classical encryption algorithms based on prime factorization, highlighting the need for quantum-resistant alternatives. The rapid advancement of quantum technology, potentially surpassing the growth rate of classical computation, further emphasizes the urgency of this transition.

The results of the research provide a foundation for understanding the challenges that quantum computing poses to cryptography. Future research should aim to overcome these limitations by utilizing real quantum hardware and mobilizing the broader cryptographic community to develop scalable, quantum-resistant solutions. The cryptographic community faces a significant challenge in safeguarding digital communications in the face of advancing

quantum technology.

Limitations

The Qiskit AER simulator could only factor semi-primes up to 25 due to entanglement simulation complexity on classical hardware. Real quantum hardware access posed logistical challenges with limited availability. Consequently, the narrow experimental scope does not fully reflect the broader cryptographic implications of quantum attacks on modern encryption systems.

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